

PERISCOPING INSTITUTIONAL CORRUPTION AND SINGLE TREASURY ACCOUNTS IN FEDERAL MINISTRIES IN ANAMBRA STATE: HOW CAN IT BE JUSTIFIED?

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19660391>

Keywords:

Treasury Single Account, Institutional corruption, drain pipe, administration

Abstract: *Single Treasury Account (TSA) policy was initiated by Good Luck Jonathan administration and was eventually put into use in 2015 by Muhammadu Buhari administration. The primary objective of this fiscal policy was to address fund leakages and institutional corruption in the public sphere. Therefore the broad objective of the study was to examine the nexus between Institutional corruption and Single Treasury Account execution. Two federal Ministries in Anambra state formed the place of study. The study adopted survey research. Data were elicited using questionnaire, in-depth interview, focus group discussion guide. The two hypotheses formulated were all rejected thus making the null hypotheses acceptable. However the study recommended that there should be the overall implementation of TSA should be pragmatic and the implementers subjected to mandatory training to enable them have psychological re-orientation, to enable them understand that stealing is stealing whether it is government money or private property. Further researches are recommended to enable the researchers unravel the actual inhibitors to the workability of TSA in Nigeria.*

Introduction

A treasury single account (TSA) is a unified structure of government bank accounts enabling one consolidated view of cash flow, usually managed by a Central bank. It consolidates all government agency revenues into a single account, reducing borrowing costs, preventing revenue leakage, and improving transparency in public sector financial management.

Key features of TSA includes:

- (i) Centralized control: All government receipts and payments are processed through a single, centralized account system,
- (ii) Improved Cash Management: It allows the government to manage its cash resources effectively, minimizing the need for borrowing.
- (iii) Increased Transparency: By centralizing funds, it enhances oversight of ministries, departments and agencies (MDAs), reducing fraud and corruption risks.

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(iv) Elimination of idle funds: It prevents funds from sitting idle in multiple commercial bank accounts, allowing for optimal liquidity.

(v) TSA is considered a critical public financial management reform, recommended by the International Monetary Fund (IMF) to enhance accountability and efficiency, notably implemented fully in Nigeria in 2015 by the former President of Nigeria, Muhammadu Buhari.

The importance of introducing the mechanism of treasury single account cannot be overemphasized. This is because the core importance or significance of treasury single account is primarily to ensure accountability of government revenue, enhance transparency and avoid misappropriation of public funds. The introduction of treasury single account is also believed to enhance performance in the public sector especially in the area of service delivery and productivity. However, despite the introduction of TSA in Nigeria, cases of corruption are still prevalent in the Nigerian public sector. In 2016, the then Secretary to the Federal Government of Nigeria, Babachir Lawal was indicted in a N200 million contract scandal for clearing intrusive plant species in internally displaced camps in Yobe State, a North Eastern state in Nigeria. Also, in 2018 the Director General of the National Emergency Management Agency (NEMA) in Nigeria, Mustapha Maihaja was indicted for mismanaging N5.8 Billion Intervention Fund earmarked for interventions in the North Eastern part of the country (Stober 2019). Although most of these cases were investigated and actions were taken respectively,

the fact that they came up in the first place indicates that the Nigerian public sector is still faced with accountability, fund misappropriation and corruption problems, and this has continued to affect the public perception of the effectiveness of government strategies to fight corruption in Nigeria. TSA as one of the prominent strategies to curb mismanagement of funds and corruption in the Nigerian public sector would have effectively mitigated some of the issues of corruption that surfaced. Therefore, the fact that these cases surfaced has given rise to doubt as to the effectiveness of TSA in mitigating against corruption in Nigeria.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Nigeria after the so called political independence has been wallowing in leadership and institutional corruption which has resulted in formulating many fiscal policies to stem the tide but unfortunately none of such fiscal policies has made the intended impact. Today, a new policy has emerged, the Treasury Single Account (TSA). For over ten years of the operation of the TSA it appears that institutional and public corruption has increased. This calls to interrogate the reasonableness and impact of TSA in Nigerian scene. The situation is worrisome and need to be nipped in the bud.

A cursory look at the fiscal recklessness among the politicians, head of agencies, departments and MDAs, especially in Anambra State suggests that TSA has not ameliorated institutional corruption in Nigeria. Could it be that the loopholes are not identified and sealed up? Could it be that the head of agencies, departments and

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MDAs work as partners in crime with the powers that be?

1.3 Objectives of the Study

(1) To examine the extent the inability of the policy executors to close the fund drain pipes has causes TSA not to stamp out institutional financial crimes.

(2) To investigate if the head of MDAs are culpable in widening the gap for financial crimes of Federal Ministries in Anambra State.

1.4 Hypotheses

(1) Fiscal Policy executors inability to close the fund drain pipes is responsible for the inability of TSA to stamp out institutional financial crimes

(2) The Head of the MDAs are culpable in widening the gap for financial crimes Federal Ministries in Anambra State.

2.0 Review of Related Literature

2.1.1 Treasury Single Account

The TSA policy was first recommended by the Federal Government's Economic Reform and Governance (ERG) Programme in 2004. Also, the TSA is a part of The Public Financial Management (PFM) reforms which falls under Pillar 3 of the National Strategy for Public Service Reforms towards Vision 20:20:20 to address impediments to effective and efficient cash management. The government embraced electronic payment (e-payment) system for all its financial transaction in 2008. Consequently, the Accountant General of the Federation issued a treasury circular for its take-off on January, 1st 2009 in all MDAs (Odia & Odia, 2016, Okoroacha and Chukwuemeka , 2022).

Treasury Single Account in Nigeria became operational in 2012 under the administration of

then President Goodluck Jonathan. But not much was known about it until 2015 when President Muhammadu Buhari took over the reins of governance and the full-fledged implementation of TSA took effect with all the Federal Government Ministries, Department and Agencies. Prior to the full-fledged introduction and implementation of TSA, Nigeria paraded fragmented multiple banking systems. (Odewole, 2016). The TSA, a single pool for harvesting revenue inflows of MDAs was not Buhari's idea. It was conceived by the administration of President Goodluck Jonathan, but it remained a mere policy on paper due to lack of political will on the part of the administration to enforce it (Eme & Chukwurah, 2015). TSA was in line with a series of treasury reforms, which began in 2012, aimed at ensuring transparency and accountability in the management of the nation's finances. (Odiakosa and Chukwuemeka 2023)

The Treasury Single Account is primarily designed to bring all Government funds in bank accounts within the effective control and operational purview of the Treasury, in order to: enthrone centralized, transparent and accountable revenue management; facilitate effective cash management; ensure cash availability; promote efficient management of domestic borrowing at minimal cost; allow optimal investment of idle cash; block loopholes in revenue management; establish an efficient disbursement and collection mechanism for Government funds; improve liquidity reserve; and eliminate operational inefficiency and costs associated with maintaining multiple accounts

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across multiple financial institutions Okorocho and Chukwuemeka 2022).

Treasury Single Account is a public accounting system under which all government revenue, receipts and income are collected into one single account, usually maintained by the country's Central Bank and all payments done through this account as well. The philosophical underpinning of TSA is primarily to ensure accountability of government revenue, enhance transparency and avoid misapplication and mismanagement of public funds. The proponents of Treasury Single Account argue that it would help to ensure proper cash management by eliminating idle funds usually left with different commercial banks and in a way enhance reconciliation of revenue collection and payment (Adeolu, 2018). To Eze (2020), treasure single account is a process and tool for effective management of government's finances, banking and cash position. In accordance with the name, it pools and unifies all government accounts through a single treasury account. Eze argued that, the consolidation into a TSA paves way for the timely capture and payment of all due revenues into government coffers without the intermediation of multiple banking arrangements. This prevents revenue leakages in terms of revenue loss and mismanagement by operators of all revenue-generating agencies.

Chukwu (2020) described treasure single account (TSA) as a network of subsidiary accounts all linked to a main account such that transactions are affected in the subsidiary accounts but closing balances on these subsidiary accounts are transferred to the main

account at the end of each business day. With the implementation of the Treasury Single Account, Ministries, Agencies and Departments (MDAs) will maintain their individual accounts with the commercial banks, but daily funding of their disbursements are made from the central or main account, which is resident within the Central Bank, just as their closing balances at the end of the day are transferred to the main account.

2.1.2 TSA and the Nigerian Economy

Government sees Treasury Single Account as a useful tool to establish centralized control over its revenue through effective cash management. It enhances accountability and enables government to know how much is accruing to its accounts on a daily basis (Akande, 2015). In Nigeria, it is expected that the implementation of TSA will help tame the tide of corruption, financial leakages and embezzlement.

The implementation of Treasury Single Account (TSA) is expected to block revenue leakages within the MDAs as the Ministry of Finance will be able to monitor the inflows and outflows, hence, augment the reduction in oil revenue due to falling oil prices. CBN (2015) reasoned in the same direction and said that the implementation of TSA will enable the Ministry of Finance to monitor fund flow as no agency of government is allowed to maintain any operational bank account outside the oversight of the Ministry of Finance. The implementation of the TSA will have a positive effect on the National Economic Planning, swift and full budgetary implementation; reduce leakages and other irregularities in the MDAs, aid appropriate

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planning, data collection, analysis and timely aggregation of Federal Government Revenue. Realization of the government revenue on time causes its effective allocation.

The primary benefit of a Treasury Single Account is to provide for proper monitoring of government receipts and expenditure. In the Nigerian case, it will help to block most, if not all, the leakages that have been the bane of the economy. We have a situation where some Ministries, Departments, and Agencies manage their finances like independent empires and remit limited revenue to government treasury. But, under a properly run Treasury Single Account, it can no longer be possible, as agencies of government are meant to spend in line with duly approved budget provisions (Yusuf and Chiejina, 2015). Oyedele (2015) said that "Government should make banking arrangements for efficient management and control of government's cash resources". It should be designed to minimize the cost of government borrowing and maximize the opportunity cost of fund. TSA ensures that all money received is available for carrying out government's expenditure program and making payments on time. Many low-income countries have fragmented systems for handling government receipts and payments. In these countries, the ministry of finance/treasury lacks a unified view and centralized control over government's cash resources. As a result, this fund lies idle for extended periods in numerous bank accounts held by spending agencies while the government continues to borrow to execute its budget.

Udoma (2016) opines that maintenance of TSA will enhance funding government budget rather than depend on Federal allocation. In any economy where the budget is fully funded, the aim certainly will be accomplished. The consequence should be; improved economic system, political and social development. It is clear that a government that lacks effective control of its cash resources can pay for its institutional deficiencies in multiple ways. Some of which are as follows:

1. Idle cash balances in bank accounts often fail to earn market-related remuneration.
2. The government, being unaware of these resources, incurs unnecessary borrowing costs on raising funds to cover a perceived cash shortage.
3. Idle government cash balances in the commercial banks are not idle for the banks themselves, and can be used to extend credit (Oyedele, 2015, Chukwuemeka and Umeifekwem 2024)).
4. These have been the case with Nigerian economy. Nigeria still owes a huge amount in both external and internal debts. Therefore, the implementation of TSA will promote a healthy economic system.

2.1.3 TSA and Accountability

The concept of accountability in the public sector organizations is premised on the fact that public servants and office holders hold their positions and everything connected thereto as trusts for the people (the true and general public) who are expectedly their masters, and they must render proper, accurate and timely accounts of successes or failures to the public. Transparency

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is therefore very cardinal to accountability and it stands to good reasoning that all forms of secrecy and shady dealings detract from effective and proper practice of accountability. Accountability can be classified into: financial; administrative, political and social. But here, we are concerned with finance. Financial accountability translates to obligation on the part of an official handling resources, public office or other positions of trust to report on the intended and actual use of the resources. This calls for transparent processes and procedures to attain it (Ibietan, 2013). The old style was a financial management system that allows government agencies to operate more than 17,000 poorly monitored bank accounts. Such systems allow for financial recklessness to fester and permit a lack of accountability to go unchecked. But in a critical era like now when Nigeria clamour for transparency, probity and accountability in government financial dealings, TSA should be seen as a good instrument and an effective alternative (Chukwuemeka and Iloanya, 2023).

Transparency is the availability of information to the general public and clarity about government rules, regulations and decisions, but when the center has hands that are not clean, they don't have the moral authority to give instructions to other people. However, the full implementation of TSA is a strong political will from the presidency to curb the excesses of these unscrupulous individuals (Eme, Chukuwurah, & Emmanuel, 2015). Besides, TSA is a technological driven system and by that, technological advancement has played an important role in changing governments'

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banking practices over recent times. According to Larson & Corinne (2007) 'the banking industry has created new products that allow depositors' access to real-time account balance information and the ability to move funds electronically'. Check processing has been accelerated, and electronic payment systems expanded; the availability of electronic banking networks at commercial banks allows for very effective, virtually cost-free sweeping of balances on a daily basis.

TSA engenders relative improvement on the budget performance monitoring and evaluation which on the other hand depends on the openness of government agencies. However, the budget performance monitoring and evaluation reporting in Nigeria is exclusively on resource input and makes no attempt to assess the output and outcome of resource utilization, let alone the impact of the expenditures. But TSA has moved forward the process of Budget Performance Monitoring and Evaluation to include value for money assessment and specific outcomes with respect to progress being made for the achievement of common welfare.

TSA is principally a cash management tool for efficient management of the Government's cash position. Prior to the implementation of TSA, government was incurring finance cost on debit balances in some MDA's accounts while it was earning close to nothing on the credit balances of other MDAs. With the TSA, the net balances on all the MDA accounts will now reside with the Central Bank; hence, the government will avoid incurring interest costs when it has positive net

position (Eme, Chukuwurah, & Emmanuel, 2015).

3. Methodology

The study was essentially survey in nature and therefore data were collected from the respondents using research tools like

Table 1

Table 1: *Population of the Study*

Industry	Number of Staff
Federal Ministry of Agriculture	89
Federal Ministry of Education	198
Grand Total	287

Source: *Human Resource Department, Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Education*
Data collected were analysed using parametric statistics.

4. Data Presentation and Analysis

4.1 Questionnaire Return Rate

In the course of the study, questionnaires were distributed to the various sampled federal

Table 2: *Questionnaire Return Rate*

Ministry	Questionnaire Distributed	Questionnaire Returned	Questionnaire Return Percentage (%)
Federal Ministry of Agriculture	89	81	91
Federal Ministry of Education	198	187	94
Total	164	268	Average: 92.5%

Table 4.1 above reveals the number of questionnaires distributed to the sampled federal ministries and their corresponding return rate. It is crystal clear that the return rates are high and hence acceptable, having the

questionnaire, in-depth interview, focus group discussion guide.

Two Federal Ministries in Anambra State were studies. The population of the two ministries stood at 287 workers. See table 1 below:

ministries in Enugu state; and given the uncertainties beclouding survey studies, not all questionnaires distributed were returned and properly filled. This section of the study displays the statistics of distributed and returned questionnaire and their corresponding percentages. This is shown in table 4.1 below.

highest return rate as 94% and the lowest at 91% and the average return rate as 92.5%.

Note: The return rate was calculated with the formula given as:

$$QRR = \frac{QR}{QD} \times \frac{100}{1}$$

Where:

QRR = Questionnaire Return Rate

QR = Questionnaire Returned

QD = Questionnaire Distributed

4.2 Analysis of the Returned Questionnaires

The demographic characteristics of the respondents were carried out in this section with the application of tabled frequencies and percentages.

Table 2: Gender Distribution of the Respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	171	64
Female	97	36
Total	268	100

Source: *Field Survey, 2026.*

Table 1 reveals that 64% of the respondents are male while 36% of the respondents are female. This implies that there are more male employees among the respondents than female in the selected ministries.

4.2 Test of Hypotheses

In this section, the hypotheses stated earlier in this research were tested using probability value anchored on the regression method. Three steps were used to test the hypotheses. In step one; the hypotheses were restated in null and alternate forms. In step two, the results were analyzed

while in step three, decisions were made. The decision rule involved the rejection or acceptance of the null or alternate hypotheses based on criterion of the techniques of analysis.

4.2.1 Test of Hypothesis One

H1: Fiscal Policy executors' inability to close the fund drain pipes is responsible for the inability of TSA to stamp out institutional financial crimes

Ho: Fiscal policy executors' inability to close the fund drain pipes is not responsible for the inability of TSA to stamp out institutional financial crimes.

Presentation and Analysis of Result

Dependent Variable: institutional financial crimes

Method: Least Squares

Date: 01/10/22 Time: 19:26

Sample: 268

Included observations: 268

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	3.350808	3.400219	0.985468	0.3254
TSA	0.621192	0.032170	19.30944	0.5567
R-squared	0.609384	Mean dependent var		20.72614
Adjusted R-squared	0.607750	S.D. dependent var		81.27694
S.E. of regression	50.90364	Akaike info criterion		10.70601
Sum squared resid	619292.2	Schwarz criterion		10.73493
Log likelihood	-1288.074	Hannan-Quinn criter.		10.71766
F-statistic	372.8547	Durbin-Watson stat		1.825809
Prob(F-statistic)	0.445874			

Source: Authors' Computation Using E-views

Model Line: $FMISAP = b_0 + b_1TSA + U$

Regression Line: $FMISAP = 3.350808 + 0.621192TSA$

Where; FMISAP = Fund Misappropriation, TSA = Treasury Single Account and U = stochastic error term.

Decision Rule

The decision rule is to reject the null hypothesis (**H₀**) if the probability is less than 0.05 and to accept the null hypothesis (**H₀**) if the probability is greater than 0.05.

Decision

From the above analysis, it is clearly seen that the probability value = 0.5567 is greater than 0.05. This compels the acceptance of the null hypothesis (**H₀**) and the rejection of the alternative (**H₁**). Hence; Fiscal Policy executors' inability to close the fund drain pipes is not responsible for the inability of TSA to stamp out institutional financial crimes

in Anambra State Federal Ministries.

4.2.2 Test of Hypothesis Two

H₁: The Head of the MDAs are culpable in widening the gap for financial crimes in Federal Ministries in Anambra State.

Ho: The Head of the MDAs are not culpable in widening the gap for financial crimes in Federal Ministries in Anambra State.

Step Two: Presentation and Analysis of Result

Dependent Variable: PRF

Method: Least Squares

Date: 01/10/22 Time: 19:55

Sample: 268

Included observations: 268

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	4.165906	3.381851	1.231842	0.2192
TSA	0.622225	0.032069	19.40296	0.8740
R-squared	0.611682	Mean dependent var		21.01245
Adjusted R-squared	0.610057	S.D. dependent var		81.25610
S.E. of regression	50.74070	Akaike info criterion		10.69960
Sum squared resid	615333.7	Schwarz criterion		10.72852
Log likelihood	-1287.302	Hannan-Quinn criter.		10.71125
F-statistic	376.4749	Durbin-Watson stat		1.836720
Prob(F-statistic)	0.990231			

Source: Authors' Computation Using E-views

Model Line: $EP = b_0 + b_1TSA + U$

Regression Line: $PRF = 4.165906 + 0.622225TSA$

Where; PRF = Prompt Release of Funds, TSA = Treasury Single Account and U = Stochastic Error Term.

Decision Rule

The decision rule is to reject the null hypothesis (**Ho**) if the probability is less than 0.05 and to accept the null hypothesis (**Ho**) if the probability is greater than 0.05.

Decision

From the above analysis, it is clearly seen that the probability value = 0.8740 is greater than 0.05. This compels the acceptance of the null hypothesis (**Ho**) and the rejection of the alternative (**Ha**). Hence; The Head of the MDAs are not culpable in widening the gap for financial crimes in Federal Ministries in Anambra State federal ministries.

5. Findings, Conclusion and Recommendations

5.1 Findings

(1) Fiscal policy executors' inability to close the fund drain pipes is not responsible for the

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inability of TSA to stamp out institutional financial crimes in Anambra State Federal Ministries. The implication is that further researches should be carried out to find out the real factors that militate the inability of TSA to make the intended impact.

(2) The Heads of the MDAs are not culpable in widening the gap for financial crimes in Federal Ministries in Anambra State. Also, this requires further researches to be conducted to unravel the actual cause of the failure of TSA to stamp out corruption.

Conclusion

In 2015 the treasury single account fiscal policy was introduced to minimize corruption and close up fund drain pipes and leakages. Ministries and agencies. Prior to the introduction of treasury single account, there was high rate of institutional corruption,

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financial recklessness and broad day syphoning of public funds to private coffers in public institutions. However, based on the findings of this study, it was seen that the introduction of treasury single reduced has not not been able to stamp out institutional corruption and fund leakages in government spheres. Therefore the following recommendations have been proffered:

1. Overall the implementation of TSA should be pragmatic and the implementers subjected to mandatory training to enable them have psychological re-orientation, to enable them understand that stealing is stealing whether it is government money or private property.
2. Further researches are recommended to enable the researchers unravel the actual inhibitors to the workability of TSA in Nigeria.

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